

Welcome to the 6th volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

Hello, and welcome to the sixth edition of our Newsletter.

In this Volume we will share with you two major announcements from EU-HIP and DG-HERA, inform you about the ongoing activity of preparing a national implementations roadmap and introduce you to the project UNITED4Surveillance.

Without further ado, let's dive into the news we have prepared for you!

EU-HIP will continue it's work beyond 2025

The EU-HIP consortium continues to build a network that supports DG HERA and Member States to successfully adapt and connect with ATHINA. Gathering information on cross-border health threats has shown to be a complex task due to the heterogeneity of data being collected on multiple levels by stakeholders which have not always had the opportunity to work together and exchange information. In addition to that, existing IT systems are at different levels of maturity and complexity while participating member states also have significant differences in organizational structures and institutional authorities responsible for intelligence gathering on specific topics needed to assemble a complete picture on ongoing threats. When taking everything mentioned into account, our consortium has decided to prolong our activities in order to ensure that we will have enough time to involve all stakeholders and produce impactful outcomes. We would like to use this opportunity and thank the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) and DG HERA for their trust, support, and continued cooperation. This extension wouldn't be possible without commitment from all sides.

PROJECT EXTENDED

Until
April 2026

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What does this extension mean for us?

- More time to build on the foundations we've laid
- Deeper engagement with stakeholders and partners
- Enhanced opportunities for real-world impact
- More opportunities to develop new and enhance existing IT systems on national level
- An opportunity to bring all aspects of the EU-HIP project to a meaningful close — with impact, purpose, and a clear contribution to future health resilience across Europe

ATHINA Survey Module and Visualisation & Reporting features are Live!

Exciting news is coming from DG HERA in regard to the advancements in the development of ATHINA. On March 4th the first module went live, and DG HERA has organized an internal go-live event on 18th of March. The Survey Module along with its Visualization & Reporting features, marks a significant advancement in HERA's ability to gather health intelligence information from industries, NGOs, Member States and other Directorates-General of the EC.

What is coming next?

At the event DG HERA has confirmed that the next Modules that are expected to go live are Case Management and Collaboration. Later this year the Search and Admin functionalities are expected to be launched as well. As the development of ATHINA continues to progress, EU-HIP is making efforts to inform involved stakeholders on national level for each participating country about the new functionalities.

National roadmaps to implementations

Current work on EU-HIP focuses on delivering a roadmap on how the improvements on the national digital epidemiological surveillance infrastructure for early detection and assessment of health threats and events could be implemented, using good practice examples identified in the scope of the sustainability WP and the existing recommendations and standards used. The national roadmaps will include developing new systems and workflows as well as building on, complementing and extending existing IT systems and further digitalizing workflows.

Participating Member States are sharing plans for future activities within and beyond the scope of EU-HIP with assessment of human, financial and other resources needed, projections on timelines for implementation and information on synergies between institutions and projects in place. This will result in a comprehensive overview of ongoing and future steps that countries are taking towards better surveillance and response to health threats, facilitating cooperation between them with the aim to create more streamlined processes and resulting data in the future.

Meet the project: UNITED4Surveillance

UNITED⁴Surveillance

In a landscape of ongoing initiatives taking place in Europe and on a global scale, sometimes it gets hard to keep track of the ones that are closely related to your field of expertise and from which you could benefit, professionally and out of pure curiosity. To help you keep track while not getting overwhelmed, at the end of each Newsletter we introduce you to a project which you might find interesting. This time it's UNITED4Surveillance.

UNITED4Surveillance is an EU4Health Joint Action with 40 partners from all across Europe. The Joint Action started in January 2023 and will run until 31 December 2025. The National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) is coordinating this project.

The goal of this Joint Action is to assist member states and the EU in the deployment of digitalized and integrated surveillance systems, operating both at national and European level. With the aim to ensure better detection of early warning signs and more accurate risk assessment and coordinated response among the member states to any future cross-border health threats.

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